

Digital Citizenship Infrastructure to Foster the Reinforcement of National Identity in Indonesia

Alif Aditya Candra, Karim Suryadi, Rahmat, Siti Nurbayani

Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<i>This study was to discuss and overview the infrastructure of digital citizenship in fostering the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia. This study was acknowledged from a problem in the development of digital citizenship infrastructure which could be an instrument in observing national identity in Indonesia. The process of forming a national identity could be emphasized through various platforms in the digital citizenship infrastructure, so that the internalization of national values among Indonesian could strengthen their character as Indonesian. This study was qualitative research with a phenomenological approach, where it constructed theories and phenomena concerning the infrastructure of digital citizenship in Indonesia. The results showed that the infrastructure of digital citizenship in the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia was carried out in three ways, namely: 1) internalization of awareness on digital literacy through Citizenship Education learning, 2) implementing Habituation of national identity values in the digital citizenship infrastructure, and 3) conducting digital forums that could reinforce digital citizenship infrastructure and reinforcement of national identity.</i>
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Introduction

National identity as a national character value has experienced a crisis that has an impact on an identity crisis for every nation. Mukherjee (2018) states that the digital vision has facilitated the growth of a transparent governance infrastructure. In the same perspective, Alinejad and Ponzanesi (2020) strengthen that there is a digitally mediated experience that shapes subjectivity. Therefore, the national character value in the digital scope will be influenced by the growth of digital infrastructure.

The rapid movement of information technology creates challenges and opportunities in terms of national identity. Treré et al. (2020) state that the availability of rapid internet access has connected people to their social networks as daily experience. This can be seen from the fact that currently people have been influenced by the internet. In this case, Harvey and Ala-Fossi (2016) also argue that the commitment of internet convergence has affected communicative patterns and created new challenges in co-existing with the internet.

The digital citizenship infrastructure will participate in fostering the reinforcement of national identity of a nation. Lechner (2007) says that the re-definition of national identity has varied across sectors as a global pressure. When the phenomenon of global pressure is reviewed, a pattern of national identity will form itself with number of indicators in its definition.

Fostering national identity of citizens through digital citizenship infrastructure will follow the behavior of active citizens on digital platforms. A study of Gómez (2020) has resulted that the economy is highly the basis of digital inequality and a barrier to material access. Meanwhile, Edensor (2004) clarifies that the discussion on nation and national identity tends to focus on the cultural elite of the authoritative culture, the traditions, and the customs of their people. Therefore, it is currently important to classify the national identity of citizens through digital citizenship infrastructure.

The issue of digital citizenship infrastructure has recently been increasingly discussed and it has become a discussion in terms of culture and technological development. It purposed to realize good and civilized citizens in terms of digital citizenship infrastructure. There is a necessary to pay attention to it today's world. Moreover, the issue of national identity will meet with digital citizenship infrastructure that factually can provide a new sense in national identity. Related to this matter, when identifying social psychological patterns of the narrative composition, the results can reflect some ideal features of national identity (László et al. 2003). Meanwhile, the emergence of new media and social change has become a concern in the realm of digital citizenship (Xu, 2018), because the construction of a national identity is a negotiation between a nation's Selbstbilds and their Fremdbilds (Rusciano, 1997). Therefore, regarding the digital citizenship infrastructure, it is necessary to rethink the 'digital' aspect of national identity.

In another perspective, Jones and Mitchell (2015) have provided a clarification that digital citizenship purposes to manifest and interpret online behavior and online civic engagement of society. Besides, awareness is

constitutional (Rosana, 2014). In this case, the infrastructure of digital citizenship will create number of considerations in the construction of national identity in digital era.

As a large and diverse country in terms of national identity, Indonesia certainly faces many obstacles. Based on Law Number 24 of 2009 concerning the Flag, Language, National Symbol, and National Song, that they are positioned as national identity and the identity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. However, in term of national identity and digital citizenship infrastructure in the context of Indonesia, we find several fundamental problems, namely:

1. There is a violence and mass upheaval as a form of vertical and horizontal tension due to plural society (Apud, n.d)
2. It is necessary to formulate, define and review the concept of Indonesia national identity, as well as to measure the nationalism of Indonesian (Agung, 2017)
3. The advance of technology has a potency to shift Indonesian culture as the identity of the Indonesian (Rayta, n.d)
4. Globalization is a challenge for national identity (Kusuma, 2015)
5. Formal education should be the production of Indonesian individual identities (Kusuma, 2015)

Based on the phenomenon concerning national identity and digital citizenship infrastructure in the context of Indonesia, it should be a problem by persisting how infrastructure for digital citizenship can foster the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia. In fact, national identity characterizes a nation. Strengthening national identity is a required effort, because it is the nature of the integrity of nation and state (Rahayu, 2007). In this case, Tranter and Donoghue (2014) emphasize that the aspects of a nation's national narrative need to be studied. Therefore, in terms of national identity, a complete construction is fundamental to affirm the national identity as a nation.

In regard to previous problems, this study aims to find out the digital citizenship infrastructure that can foster the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia. It is in line with the statement of Shelley et al. (2004) that developing digital skills is positively related to digital citizenship. In one way, there is a problem in the development of digital citizenship infrastructure in observing national identity in Indonesia.

We view that digital citizenship infrastructure can foster the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia. National identity actually provides a direction to citizens, and the framework of digital citizenship (in the perspective of sociology) concerns on social cohesion with digital practices of people (Harris & Johns, 2020). Therefore, it is appropriate for digital citizenship infrastructure to foster the reinforcement of national identity to create identity awareness for citizens, so that state workers are aware of their rights and obligations in nation and state's life.

2. Materials and Methods

This study focused on the infrastructure of digital citizenship in fostering the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia. This study was descriptive qualitative research with a phenomenological approach, where it constructed theories and phenomena in the infrastructure of digital citizenship in Indonesia. The qualitative research is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written words (Moleong, 2007). The data were collected through literature studies taken from various literature related to digital citizenship infrastructure in fostering the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia.

This study was started by analyzing the phenomenon by using phenomenology perspective. Then, this study determined the subject being studied, performed data collection, note-taking, analyzed data, and carried out a written report. In the phenomenological process, this study referred to Alase's idea (2017) that phenomenology is a qualitative methodology that allows researchers to apply their subjectivity and interpersonal skills in exploratory research processes.

The final stage was data analysis which was performed through several stages, namely (a) understanding the data as a whole, (b) compiling descriptions, (c) identifying, (d) applying themes, and (e) synthesizing explanations for each theme.

3. Results and Discussion

Any comments and suggestions are welcomed so that we can constantly improve this template to satisfy all authors' research needs.

3.1. The Internalization of Digital Awareness through Citizenship Education

The awareness on digital meditation in the manifestation of digital citizenship infrastructure to foster the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia requires any support as a media for the success of the vision of digital citizenship infrastructure and national identity. In this case, educational facilities still become superior means for the Indonesian in inheriting the noble values of the nation. Moreover, the Citizenship Education learning scheme as a compulsory learning at every level of higher education – as stated in the state constitution Article 37 paragraph (1) and (2) Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning National Education System- confirms that Citizenship Education is compulsory in the curriculum of basic education, secondary education and higher

education.

Citizenship Education is useful as a subject that inherits the noble values of nation. In this case, Levinson (2003) stated that Citizenship Education is the main goal of public schools which is useful in fostering awareness of the state on its citizens. Meanwhile, the competencies that need to be developed in Citizenship Education are civic skills, civic disposition, and civic knowledge, so that to reinforce national identity and digital citizenship infrastructure, Citizenship Education should become a vehicle for internalizing digital awareness through Citizenship Education (Bronson, 1999). In this regard, we present a model for internalizing digital awareness through Citizenship Education.

Figure 1. Internalization Model of Digital Meditation Awareness through Citizenship Education

Based on Figure 1, there is an expectation that the actions undertaken in Citizenship Education learning will have an effect on citizen immediate actions. Wahab and Sapriya (2011) argue that the attitude of citizens will be effective only by fostering moral values in society. In the same view, a study by Nurdin (2017) has indicated that the development of topics in Citizenship Education is delegated to each university. Meanwhile, Ben-Porath (2007) states that patriotism should be considered as a part of citizenship that can contribute to future education policy makers. Therefore, in the internalization of digital awareness through Citizenship Education is supposed that citizen behaviour will produce an effective result through fostering moral values in Citizenship Education.

Furthermore, the internalization of digital awareness through Citizenship Education will be useful in strengthening citizenship identity in the digital citizenship infrastructure. In this case, McCosker and Johns (2014) state that social media can be an example of digital awareness which can allow a variety of creativity, cultural expression, public, and civic participation. However, unexpectedly, there are various consequences, particularly in citizenship identity.

To reconsider, digital awareness is necessary to foster, guide and direct the attitude of citizens in digital media. Despite some developments in various international jurisdictions, there must still be policies and practices of educators, online communities and social media networks to fulfil the commitment of digital equal citizenship (Henry & Powell, 2016). Moreover, when the internet provides various ways for discussion, the internet – accessing skills need to be provided to anyone who uses the media (Beam et al. 2018).

It is undeniable that Citizenship Education is a representative to build digital literacy awareness to realize national identity. In this regard, Sandu (2015) states that currently, society is undergoing a process of progressive transformation of globalization space. Therefore, preparing active citizens is one of the main goals in higher education (Evans et al. 2018). Besides, Citizenship Education cannot ignore any involvement in digital literacy to create competent citizens.

The benefits of digital literacy awareness can be gained by using social media as an educational medium for the community in delivering digital learning for the sake of society. Georgiou (2019) states that the digital order needs protection, and that security and privacy should underline technology users in contemporary society (Norval, 2018). Therefore, an awareness of digital literacy is carried out as a prerequisite for strengthening digital citizenship infrastructure.

Digital literacy awareness in Citizenship Education is an important part of advancing participation in society. In this case, Menezes (2003) states that participation is considered as a crucial dimension of citizenship. In addition, Citizenship Education should provide education with a recommendation for policies and programs in the context of civic events (Purnell et al. 2016). Therefore, the awareness of digital literacy in Citizenship Education in Indonesia has become a civilian experience that has opened up freedom and encouraged changes in several aspects of national life and the beginning of the development of democracy in the context of Indonesia.

The expansion of democracy in the awareness of digital literacy on Citizenship Education has made it successful in dealing with political transitions that occur in national life. Witschge and Werfhorst (2019) address

that civic and political involvement are linked to participation in higher education. Meanwhile, understanding the geographic dimensions of citizenship can foster democracy through contemporary digital activism (Baek, 2018). Therefore, the awareness of digital literacy in Citizenship Education will enable individuals to take a part in civilian life.

3.2. The Habituation of National Identity Values in the Digital Citizenship Infrastructure

The values of national identity in digital citizenship infrastructure need to be introduced to society through various means. Dougherty (2018) claims that the concept of development refracts a collection of individual values and maps to societal attitudes. Besides, a dramatic change is possibly carried out by showing a level of prejudice (Durrheim et al. 2011). Therefore, the customization of national identity values in a digital citizenship infrastructure requires a method that can be embedded in citizens; not only knowledge itself.

In the Indonesian context, the Habituation of national identity values in digital citizenship infrastructure is reflected in the form of communicating on social media which should still use tradition as Indonesian. It means that in digital activity, citizens must still uphold the values of nation and state. In this case, Lau (2014) argued that this type of political discourse will benefit in reviving the political imagination of society. Therefore, the Habituation of national identity values needs to be realized and used as a manifestation of digital citizenship infrastructure in Indonesia. The following figure is a model of Habituation of the values of national identity in the digital citizenship infrastructure.

Figure 2. The Habituation Model of National Identity Values in Digital Citizenship Infrastructure

The previous figure has given an indication that practically, the citizenship infrastructure which is often considered inappropriate in national identity schemes has commonly led to strengthen national identity. Chow and Kennedy (2015) argue that there are number of variations in civic engagement among young citizens. Meanwhile, a study of Miranda et al. (2017) has found that a conceptual model that includes a community dimension and civic dimension was proposed in all countries, so that the Habituation of national identity values in digital citizenship infrastructure becomes an important thing in the study of national identity.

The Habituation of national identity values is still minimum and should be taken into a concern in the Indonesian context. This phenomenon is indicated by the presence of passive community participation in taking any (media) has played an important role in informing young people about politics. The results of a study on debate programs on television in influencing the normative democratic attitudes of young citizens also reveal that debates strengthen the effectiveness of political information for young citizens. Therefore, familiarizing values of national identity can increase community participation which can be carried out by its function as citizens.

The values of national identity are considered capable to overcome the problem of moral degradation in a nation, because the movement of national identity increasingly characterizes the attitude of citizens. Cammaerts et al. (2013) state that the low level of voter participation among young people does not mean that they are a selfish generation. In line with it, a longitudinal study by McKinney et al. (2013) on the democratic attitudes of young citizens has found that the effectiveness of political information can be increased by campaign. However, the values of national identity that are accustomed will be able to form a complete character of citizens.

The Habituation of national identity values in the digital citizenship infrastructure will re-affirm the digital citizenship infrastructure. A result of a study by Shelley et al. (2004) emphasize that some attitudes towards technology have a direct impact on digital citizens. Moreover, a rights-based approach to digital media has offered a framework for balancing online protection (Livingstone, 2017). Therefore, the value of national identity in the digital citizenship infrastructure scheme is a new media for positioning citizens for affirming national identity.

3.3. A Digital Forum that Can Strengthen Digital Citizenship Infrastructure and National Identity

Digital citizenship infrastructure in reinforcing national identity without digital forums will not materialize (Pengrum, 2010), and it is a common sense in today's world. Alinejad and Ponzanesi (2020) state that emotion can help more comprehensively on digital mediation in social life. Therefore, digital citizenship infrastructure has

become one of the means in reinforcing national identity.

In the context of Indonesian, the existence of digital forums in the digital citizenship infrastructure to reinforce national identity is an instrument to contribute for world relations. The following is a figure of President Joko Widodo in his meeting with Australian Prime Minister Malcom Turnbull.

Figure 3. The President Joko Widodo in His Meeting with the Australian Prime Minister Malcom Turnbull in the Signing of the Jakarta Concord at the 2017 Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA) Summit

The existence of digital forum allows Indonesian to show their existence as a nation. To execute it, we need a sufficient spectrum in terms of conveying information and cultural assets (Harvey & Ala-Fossi, 2016). Besides, in social science analysis, the digital gap allows majority of people to strengthen their ability to survive (Mansell, 2002). In line with it, Kuntsman and Miyake (2019) state that the concept of '*digital disengagement*' has number of implications for the relationship between digital media, culture and society. Therefore, the existence of a digital forum is important to reinforce the identity of nation.

The digital forum is a vehicle (media) to reinforce national identity, because it can minimize any passive attitude of the community in state civil affairs. Hidayah et al. (2020) argue that civil society intelligence is accommodated in action. Moreover, building citizen intelligence requires media (Candra & Suryadi, 2020), so that digital forums will be important to inform the public about their rights and obligations as citizens.

Martini et al. (2018) state that technology leads to the intelligence of citizens, because digital forum is one of the products of globalization. Contrary, communication and expression are limited by a new digital system (Plantin et al. 2016), so that the challenges and limitations of digital participatory practice should be overcome through alternative participant-centered approach (Pawluczuk et al. 2018). Thus, in terms of reinforcing Indonesian's national identity through digital forums, there will be many reactions and results that are going to emerge.

Based on a reality that Indonesia is still far from an ideal atmosphere in terms of reinforcing national identity due to the lack of public participation, facilities, and literacy awareness. van Doorn (2019) states that by mobilizing its user-base, a community can get many opportunities by technology support. On the other hand, by citizens themselves, the discourse of pragmatic practices of social rights, political citizenship, and common good will have been accommodated (Cardullo & Kitchin, 2018). In this view, the ideal atmosphere of reinforcing national identity will continue to develop.

The track of Indonesian to achieve an ideal atmosphere in the reinforcement of national identity through digital citizenship infrastructure will affect the attitude of integrity as evidence by factual data, because that in future times, Indonesia needs people who can foster any development (Darmawan, 2015). By this, in the dimension of digital citizenship infrastructure, society will experience number of dynamics during Indonesia's political tracks which continue to experience any growth; moreover by the voice of the government is the dream of all countries which can support publics' aspiration (Darmawan, 2015).

Strictly speaking, in the scope of digital citizenship infrastructure in Indonesia, (for many respects) the attitude

of public participation will increase. Digital practice will encourage identity management (Udwan et al. 2020), while Irani (2015) states that this commitment is in line with politics and social, and that mass democracy is constructed in a circle of coalition across variety of differences. Therefore, the infrastructure scope for digital citizenship in Indonesia will be a means of developing, expanding, and constructing a digital citizenship infrastructure and national identity

Conclusion

Digital citizenship infrastructure in fostering the reinforcement of national identity in Indonesia is in line with the development of digital citizenship infrastructure instruments in observing national identity. The view of digital citizenship infrastructure shows that in the implementation of national life, it still provides the noble values of the nation as a historical legacy. However, internalizing digital awareness through Citizenship Education learning is a process in the formation of national identity in Indonesia which can be emphasized through various platforms in the digital citizenship infrastructure, so that the internalization of national values for Indonesian will be able to strengthen their character.

The Habituation of national identity values in the digital citizenship infrastructure will be in line with the inhabiting national identity values that can be applied in society and digital environment. Besides, digital forums can reinforce the infrastructure of digital citizenship and national identity to produce good, intelligent, and wise character in performing digital activities.

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Author Information

Alif Aditya Candra

Department of Citizenship Education, Indonesia
University of Education, Bandung, 40154
Indonesia

Karim Suryadi

Department of Citizenship Education, Indonesia
University of Education, Bandung, 40154
Indonesia

Rahmat

Department of Citizenship Education, Indonesia
University of Education, Bandung, 40154
Indonesia

Siti Nurbayani

Department of Citizenship Education, Indonesia
University of Education, Bandung, 40154
Indonesia